

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13832583

Effects Of Think-Pair Share And Problem-Based Instructional Strategies On Students Interest In Biology In Taraba State, Nigeria

¹Dr. Danjuma G. Stella (PhD) & ²Geoffrey Gabriel

¹Department of Science Education, Taraba State University Jalingo, Taraba State, Nigeria
stellagdanjuma@gmail.com

²Lau Local Government Universal Basic Education Authority, Nigeria
gabrielgeoffrey43@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The study investigated the Effects of Think-pair share and problem-Based Instructional strategies on students Interest in Biology in Taraba State, Nigeria. The population of the study consisted of 2971 secondary school two (SS2) Biology students. A sample of (144) SS2 students were used for the study. This research work adopted a quasi-experimental research design involving pretest, posttest and post-posttest group design. One research Questions and one null hypothesis were formulated, one instrument Students Interest in Biology Scale (SIBS) developed by the researcher was used for data collection. (SIBS) was subjected to content and face validation. The reliability of the instruments was established using Kuder-Richardson (K-20) to be 0.88 for SIBS was obtained. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research question while Analysis of Covariance ANCOVA was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. One of the results obtained shows that there was no significant difference in the mean interest score of students in Biology when taught using Think-pair share. It was concluded that Think-pair Share is very effective for the teaching and learning of Biological concepts in secondary school and proven from the result to be more effective. It is recommended among others that based on the findings of this study that: Biology teachers should be encouraged to adopt Think-pair Share Instructional Strategy while teaching Biology, workshops and seminars should be organized for Biology teachers to motivate them enlighten them on the use of Think-Pair Share Instructional Strategy.

Keywords: Interest, Think-Pair Share, Problem-Based Instruction.

INTRODUCTION

Biology is an integral part of science that focuses on living things (plants and animals). And also, prerequisite subject for many sciences related fields of specialty such as medicine, forestry, nursing, agriculture, biotechnology and others. Which contributes immensely to the technological growth of the nation? Effective study of Biology in secondary school can equips students with useful concepts, principles and theories that will enable them solve life problems before and after their graduation (Olufemi & Ibikun4 2015) which is very important in today's society.

This implies that the learners would become useful to themselves and the society as well as capable of going for further studies in biology related discipline. Obioha (2022) submitted that the subject is a fascinating study that ranges from microscopic-cellular molecules to the biosphere, encompassing the earth's surface and its living organisms. Biology is also branch of science that deals with the study of living things, which includes human-beings (Michael, 2018). Biology has many branches which

include; zoology, botany, ecology, genetics, morphology, anatomy, physiology, histology, microbiology, evolution, cell biology to mention but a few. Many societal issues today are biologically-based. These include biodiversity, genetically modified organisms, reproductive technologies, and prolongation of life, food production, tourism industry (biological gardens) and processing industries. All of these issues have involved improvements that meet human needs and so the twenty first century has been considered as ‘the age of biology’ (Reiss, 2018). The knowledge of biology helps in checking environmental degradation such as desertification, erosion, water hyacinth and pollution among others.

The cardinal objectives of biology education are to prepare students to acquire adequate laboratory and field skills in biology, meaningful and relevant knowledge in biology, ability to apply scientific knowledge to everyday life in matter of personal, community health and agriculture, lastly reasonable and functional scientific attitudes (Federal Ministry of Education, 2014).). The stated objectives show the effort of the Nigerian educational sector towards scientific development of the nation. However, a close observation of students’ results at West African Secondary School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) and research report in biology shows that these laudable objectives are yet to be achieved. Students’ performance in the subject from West African Secondary School Certificate Examination (WASSCE) has been poor (Bajon, 2015). This submission insinuates that student’s interest, in biology need to be looked into. To do this, science education need to find out the effects of teaching strategies on students learning process which have to do with their interest, ability in the subject.

Persistent use of traditional teaching methods in Biology classrooms has been advanced and become the underlying factor for students’ poor performance in the subject (Filgona, 2016). This is not to say that the use of traditional method in teaching and learning over the years has not yielded any positive results. Clark and Wareham (2013) observed that Biology teachers have been using traditional teaching method than many other subjects and its usage has expanded further over the last few years. According to Arokoyu and Chukwu (2017), traditional method which is predominantly used in secondary schools in Nigeria contributes to the poor academic performance in Biology. Hence, the need to use innovative instructional strategies such as: think-pair-share and problem-based instruction amongst others.

According to Okam and Zakari, (2017), Research findings have shown that, compared to other subjects, there is a relatively strong relationship between interest in Biological concepts. Interest is what an individual makes out of the situation on ground due to the value attached to a particular thing. It means that a child could develop interest in any object or activity that is found to be attractive or stimulating to him. Therefore, in a classroom situation, the learner will be attentive during a lesson only if the instruction is of interest to the learner. The curiosity and interest of the students, according to Aydin & Coskun (2013) manifest itself in the performance and retention ability of the students.

Lyman (2019) Think-Pair-Share model has been selected for this study which was developed as a constructivist model for certain reasons. First and foremost, Think-Pair-Share pedagogy allows the learning to be less teacher centered by giving more interdependence to students for participating in the activities, which is what a communicative-approach driven language class, thus an environment where learning becomes more meaningful and empowers. Moreover, this technique offers “processing time” and gives students “wait-time”, which greatly helps students to go beyond and deeper in their thinking and thus their answers similar to what Yerigan (2018) writes “The Think-Pair-Share is an active learning strategy that provides processing time for 10:2 theory, builds in wait time, provides rehearsal, enhances depth and breadth of thinking, increases level of participation, allows the instructor to check for understanding and provides time for instructor to make instructional decisions”. Its rationale has a lot in common with that of the constructivist approach as this model requires learners to interact with each other/others at different levels. Therefore, this model encourages learners to be more active during instruction.

The original Think-Pair-Share model fundamentally consists of 3 steps.

Firstly, the teacher initially posits a question to the class and gives students time to think individually and come up with original answers on their own. The second step requires students’ pairing up preferably with the student sitting closest to them. At that point, depending on the type of the task and the question, students share their primary thoughts or answers with each other and the third and final step, students, or now pairs, share what they agree on with the whole class. This can be done in the traditional way where the teacher elicits the answers from one or more couples

Problem-based Instruction (PBI) is a term used for a range of pedagogical approaches that encourage students to learn through the structured exploration of a research problem. It is an active instructional strategy which enables the student to become aware of what is learnt and determines his/her problem-solving ability. Problem-based strategy of Instruction helps to determine learning needs. It is able to make knowledge operative and to perform group works “in the face of real-life problems” (Ongowo & Indoshi, 2013). This implies that the strategy requires students to become responsible for their own learning with the teacher playing the role of a facilitator. The instructional strategy portrays teacher’s intervention in the learning process which diminishes as students progressively take on responsibility for their own learning processes which determines to some extent the level of students’ mastery of the acquired knowledge. This shows that the use of this strategy in teaching biology concept could improve students in the subject since the use of the strategy determines to some extent the level of students’ mastery and acquire knowledge.

Gender is a psychological term, which describes behaviors and attributes expected of individual on the basis of being a male or female. An issue that has occupied the frontage of science education for many years is that of gender disparity in science performances of secondary school students. Gender factor is very strong in learning and thus determines the interest, performance and consequent career choice. Some scholars have reported that gender influences student’s performance in Biology. The controversies on gender in the school performance and classroom behavior according to Hassaskhah and Zamir (2013) have continued to be inconclusive. This calls for more research on the issue of gender parity and disparity in teaching and learning.

Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of the study was to find out the effect of think-pair-share and problem-based instructional strategies on students’ interest, in biology in Jalingo. Taraba State. Specifically, the study intended to find out: -

- i. The relative effects of think-pair-share instructional strategies on students’ interest in biological concepts.
- ii. The relative effects of problem-based instructional strategies on students’ interest in biological concepts.

Research Question

The following research question was used to guide the study:

- i. What is the interest mean score of students taught biology using think-pair-share instructional strategy?
- ii. What is the interest mean score of students taught biology using problem-based instructional strategy?

Statement of Hypothesis

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H0₁: There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of students taught biological concepts using think-pair-share instructional strategy.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of students taught biological concepts using problem-based instructional strategy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The design of the study was quasi-experimental design. Specifically, it is a comparative pre-test, post-test, and post-post-test of non-equivalent group design. This research design is used to establish cause and effect relationships between two or more variables. Therefore, since this study tends to compare more than two variables such as think-pair share, problem-based instructional strategies on students’ interest of biological concept. The population of this study was 2971 secondary school II within jalingo education zone Taraba state, Nigeria. Simple random sampling was used in selecting two (2) secondary school. The two schools were designated experimental group. The sample size was 144 students of Biology selected from two (2) intact classes.

The instrument used: (a) Students’ Interest Biology Scale (SIBS). It contains Twenty-eight (28) items designed to determine students’ interest in Biology. It was four-point rating scale.

The experimental group one (1) received instruction using think-pair share strategy and the experimental group two (2) also received instruction using problem based instructional strategy, the

treatment was used to determine the effectiveness of the two instructional strategies but particularly the effect of the treatment on the two experimental group.

RESULTS

Research Question

What is the interest mean score of students taught biology using think-pair-share and problem-based instructional strategy?

Table 1: Mean interest score of students taught biology using think-pair-share and problem-based instructional strategy

Group	N	Pre-Interest		Post-Interest		Mean Gain
		Mean	Std. Dev	Mean	Std. Dev	
Think-pair-share	61	2.60	0.19	2.71	0.20	0.19
Problem-based	83	2.39	0.22	2.58	0.18	0.11
Mean Differences						
		0.21		0.13		0.8

Table 1 shows the mean scores and standard deviations in the interest scores of students taught biology using the Think-pair-share instructional strategy and those taught using Problem-based instructional strategy. It is observed that the mean interest scores of students in the Think-pair-share instruction group are higher than the Problem-based instructional strategy group. This implies that the use of Think-pair-share instructional strategy favored students more than the Problem-based instructional strategy.

H0₁: There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of students taught biological concepts using think-pair-share and problem-based instructional strategy.

Table 10: One-way Analysis of Covariance of the Mean Interest Scores of Think-pair-share and Problem-based instructional strategy

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	.866 ^a	2	.433	12.021	.000	.146
Intercept	4.673	1	4.673	129.702	.000	.479
PRE-INTEREST	.244	1	.244	6.761	.010	.046
GROUP	.247	1	.247	6.859	.010	.046
Error	5.080	141	.036			
Total	1005.885	144				
Corrected Total	5.947	143				

a. R Squared = .146 (Adjusted R Squared = .134)

Table 10 is one-way ANCOVA between groups’ analysis of covariance to compare the effect of think-pair-share instructional Strategy and problem-based instructional strategy on students’ Interest in biological concepts. The result $F(1, 141) = 6.859, P = .010 < 0.05$ shows that the two groups differ significantly. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is a significant difference in the mean interest scores of students taught biological concepts using think-pair-share and problem-based instructional strategy. The effect size (eta square = .046) is high and it indicates that 4.6% of the difference in the mean score is based on the strategy used.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding showed that the mean interest scores of students in the Think-pair-share instruction group is 2.60 in pretest and 2.71 in posttest, while their standard deviations are 0.19 and 0.20 for student interest scale. Students in the Problem-based instructional strategy group have the mean interest scores of 2.39 and 2.58 in pretest and posttest respectively and standard deviations of 0.22 and 0.18. This

implies that the use of think pair share instructional strategy was better than the problem based strategy.

The result of this study is in line with that of Obiokwe (2008) Knogler (2014), itoodoo and Emmanuel (2019) and Onu et.al (2020) who study student's interest in biology affirm that students taught biological concept using think-pair share instructional strategy show more level of interest than their counterpart who taught biology using problem-based instructional strategy. And this finding disagrees with that of Omega (2017) which showed that problem-Based Instructional Strategy had a more positive effect on students Interest.

From the finding of this study, think-pair share instructional strategy is more attractive and was able to capture the interest of the students due to free and meaningful interaction between the paired group which foster interest and conceptual development. More so, interest to a large extent contains the influence of students' activities. However, think-pair share instructional strategy is interesting due to its unique pairing of students for effective teaching and learning in biology. It also motivates learner and arouse their interest for better result as such biology teachers can adopt the use of think-pair share instruction during biology lesson.

CONCLUSIONS

On the basis of the outcome of the study, it can be significantly concluded that

1 Think-pair share instructional strategy has been proven to arouse students' interest in Biology as such Biology teachers can adopt the use of Think-pair share during Biology lessons.

RECOMMENDATIONS

On the basis of this study, the researcher put forward the following recommendations:

1. Ministry of Education and school proprietors should ensure that teachers of Biology are trained to adopt modern effective teaching strategies such as Think-pair share instructional strategy through sponsorship to workshops, seminars and even further trainings as this will enhance the teaching and learning of Biology
2. School supervisors and Heads of schools should ensure that the use of Think-pair share instructional strategy is encouraged and recommended in all schools for the effective implementation of the Biology curriculum by regular supervision and monitoring

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